

Efficacy, IHS Guideline Adherence, and Methodological Quality of Non-invasive Neuromodulation Clinical Trials in Migraine and Cluster Headache: A Systematic Review (Protocol)

The protocol and materials will be deposited on Zenodo with a timestamp (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17566912)

Javiera Canales-Rodríguez¹; Cornelius Angerhöfer²; Edoardo Caronna^{1,3}; Bianca Raffaelli^{2,4}; Lucas Hendrik Overeem²; Patricia Pozo-Rosich^{1,3} and Uwe Reuter^{2,5}

1. Headache Clinic, Neurology Department, Hospital Universitari Vall d'Hebron, Department of Medicine, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain
2. Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin, corporate member of Freie Universität Berlin and Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Department of Neurology, Berlin, Germany
3. Headache and Neurological Pain Research Group, Vall d'Hebron Research Institute, Barcelona, Spain
4. Clinician Scientist Program, Berlin Institute of Health (BIH), Berlin, Germany
5. Universitätsmedizin Greifswald, Greifswald, Germany

Corresponding Author:

Patricia Pozo-Rosich, MD PhD
Ps. Vall d'Hebron 119-129
08035, Barcelona – Spain
patricia.pozo@vallhebron.cat

Contributions

UR and PP-R: conceptualised the review; JC-R and CA: protocol design, PICO, methods; EC, BR, LH-O, JC-R and CA: search and data extraction; CA: methodological quality appraisal and evidence certainty assessment; JC-R: synthesis and drafting. All authors reviewed and approved the final version. Guarantor: UR and PP-R.

Amendments

Any amendments will be dated and versioned in the Zenodo repository.

Support

No external funding. No sponsor. The study was conducted as an academic work. The funder/sponsor role is not applicable.

INTRODUCTION

Rationale

Non-invasive neuromodulation is increasingly used for the acute and preventive treatment of migraine and cluster headache (CH). The literature shows considerable heterogeneity in study design (double-blind, sham-controlled randomised clinical trials, open-label studies, and real-world evidence), assessment criteria, and timing of evaluation. The International Headache Society (IHS) guidelines, published in 2021 for migraine and in 2022 for CH, standardises the main outcomes and assessment timing; however, many trials predate these documents. It is necessary to compare historical results with current IHS reference parameters.

Objectives (PICO)

- **Population:** Adults with migraine (with/without aura; episodic/chronic) or cluster headache (episodic/chronic) diagnosed per ICHD-3.
- **Interventions:** Non-invasive neuromodulation devices (e.g., transcutaneous, transcranial, external).
- **Comparators:** Sham device, usual care, or active control.
- **Outcomes:**
 - **Migraine acute**
Pain freedom at 2 hours, before the use of any rescue medication.
Freedom from the most bothersome symptom (MBS) at 2 hours.
 - **Migraine preventive:**

Change from baseline in the number of migraine days over a pre-specified period.
 - Change from baseline in the number of moderate/severe headache days over a pre-specified period.
 - 50% responder rate for the reduction of migraine days over a pre-specified period.
 - **Cluster acute:**
Pain-freedom at 15 minutes without recurrence of any level of pain within 3 hours in the first treated attack.
 - **Episodic Cluster preventive:**
Change from baseline in the number of weekly attacks for the entire double-blind phase.
 - **Chronic Cluster preventive:**
Primary endpoint:

Change from baseline in the number of monthly attacks for the entire double-blind phase or for pre-specified periods within the double-blind phase.

METHODS

Eligibility criteria

Population:

Inclusions: Adults (≥ 18 years) with migraine (with/without aura; episodic/chronic) or cluster headache (episodic/chronic) diagnosed according to the International Classification of Headache Disorders, third edition (ICHD-3).

Exclusions: Secondary headache disorders (e.g., post-traumatic, cervical injury, infection, substance withdrawal, non-specific/facial pain) and paediatric populations (< 18 years).

Interventions:

Inclusions: Non-invasive neuromodulation devices (transcutaneous, transcranial or external). Examples include external trigeminal nerve stimulation, non-invasive vagus nerve stimulation, single-pulse transcranial magnetic stimulation, remote electrical neuromodulation and similar technologies.

Exclusions: invasive, implanted, percutaneous or surgically delivered neuromodulation.

Comparators:

Sham device, usual care, or active control (device or pharmacological).

Outcomes:

Trials must report at least one clinical efficacy endpoint. Safety outcomes (adverse events, serious adverse events, discontinuations) will be extracted when reported but are not required for eligibility.

Study design:

Inclusions: Original reports of human interventional clinical trials randomised or non-randomised (e.g., parallel-group, crossover, double-blind/sham-controlled, open-label interventional).

Exclusions: observational studies, diagnostic accuracy studies, review articles, editorials, letters without primary data, and secondary/sub-analyses of a parent trial already included (the most complete/primary report will be retained in cases of overlap).

Setting:

Any clinical setting (outpatient, emergency, or inpatient), any country or healthcare system.

Time frame:

Studies published between 1 January 1990 and 1 October 2024. Trial registry records within this window will be used to facilitate study identification and de-duplication; however, unpublished or non-peer-reviewed registry entries are not eligible for inclusion.

Language and publication status:

Inclusions: English-language, peer-reviewed full-text articles.

Exclusions: non-peer-reviewed sources (e.g., conference abstracts, proceedings, news items), theses, and unpublished registry entries.

Information sources

We will identify records from bibliographic databases: MEDLINE (via PubMed) and Embase (via Ovid®), and from trial registries: ClinicalTrials.gov and the World Health Organization International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO-ICTRP).

Coverage period: 1 January 1990 to 1 October 2024.

Search strategy

1) MEDLINE (via PubMed)

(neuromodulation[tiab] OR neurostimulation[tiab] OR stimulation[tiab])

AND

(migraine[tiab] OR headache[tiab])

NOT review[pt]

Filters to apply:

Language: English

Publication dates: 1990/01/01 - 2024/10/01

2) Embase (via Ovid)

1. neuromodulation.ti,ab.

2. neurostimulation.ti,ab.

3. stimulation.ti,ab.

4. 1 OR 2 OR 3

5. migraine.ti,ab.

6. headache.ti,ab.

7. 5 OR 6

8. 4 AND 7

9. 8 NOT review.pt.

10. limit 9 to english language

11. limit 10 to yr="1990 - 2024"

3) Trial registries

ClinicalTrials.gov

- Condition/Disease: (“migraine” OR “headache”)
- Other terms (Intervention): (“neuromodulation” OR “neurostimulation” OR “stimulation”).
- Age: Adult (18–64), Older Adult (65+)
- Sex: All
- Recruitment: All
- Study Results: All
- Dates: First posted (o Start date) from 1990-01-01 to 2024-10-01
- Country/Location: All

WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO-ICTRP)

- Condition: migraine OR headache
- Intervention: neuromodulation OR neurostimulation OR stimulation.
- Study type: Interventional.
- Recruitment status: All.
- Date limits: 1990–2024.

Data management

All records from MEDLINE/PubMed, Embase/Ovid, ClinicalTrials.gov, and WHO-ICTRP will be exported to a reference manager and a shared master spreadsheet. Automatic and manual deduplication will be applied using a combination of title, first author, year, DOI/PMID, and/or registration ID. We will maintain a version log with the date and responsible party. Full-text PDFs and appendices will be stored in a folder structured by device and indication. The PRISMA workflow will be updated at each stage (identification, screening, eligibility, inclusion), and a complete record of exclusion reasons will be maintained.

Selection process

Two reviewers will independently screen titles and abstracts according to predefined eligibility criteria, followed by an independent assessment of the full text of potentially eligible records. Discrepancies will be resolved by consensus; a third reviewer will mediate unresolved conflicts. Reasons for exclusion of the full text will be coded using a controlled list (e.g., No non-invasive intervention, Observational study, No ICHD criteria applied). Study selection will be documented in a PRISMA flow diagram. If the data are sufficiently homogeneous, studies meeting the eligibility criteria will be included in the quantitative synthesis; otherwise, they will be included in the structured narrative synthesis.

Data collection process

A standardised and previously agreed-upon data extraction matrix will be used. Two reviewers will extract the data independently; discrepancies will be resolved by a third reviewer. For missing or ambiguous data, authors and/or record holders will be contacted

(two attempts). Whenever available, results will be extracted for the analysis population, prioritising intention-to-treat analysis.

Data items

We will extract the following variables, grouped and defined a priori:

Study Bibliographic Information

Study title; first author; year of publication; journal; country; trial registry ID.

Trial design

Design, phase, randomisation (yes/no), blinding (yes/no), control type (sham, active, usual care/no intervention), baseline duration, double-blind duration, open-label extension (yes/no; duration), number of attacks treated per protocol (acute trials), rescue medication allowed (rules and timing).

Population

- Diagnosis per ICHD (migraine with/without aura; episodic/chronic; cluster headache episodic/chronic).
- For cluster headache: whether IHS-recommended entry criteria were applied (≥ 2 previous bouts; usual bout ≥ 4 weeks).
- Medication-overuse included.
- Sample size (enrolled and analysed), sex distribution, minimum/maximum/median age.
- Concomitant preventives permitted (yes/no; which).

Intervention

Neuromodulation type (e.g., transcutaneous/transcranial/external), application site, treatment method (key parameters where available), number of applications per day, duration of each application, frequency of use (for prevention).

Comparator

Sham/active/usual care.

Outcomes and adherence to IHS guidance

For each study, according to the indication under evaluation (migraine, acute; migraine, preventive; cluster headache, acute; cluster headache, preventive), we will record whether IHS recommended primary or secondary endpoint was assessed and whether the prespecified primary and secondary outcomes were met.

Safety and regulatory

- Adverse events.
- Regulatory status: FDA cleared (yes/no); CE marked (yes/no).

Outcomes and prioritization

Primary outcomes

- **Migraine acute:** Pain freedom at 2 hours after treatment, before the use of any rescue medication. Rationale: patient-centred, validated, and the IHS reference standard for acute efficacy.
- **Migraine preventive:** Change from baseline in monthly migraine days over the pre-specified period. Rationale: core preventive endpoint reflecting clinically meaningful burden reduction and aligned with IHS.
- **Cluster headache acute:** Pain freedom at 15 minutes without recurrence within 3 hours in the first treated attack. Rationale: time-critical disease and IHS recommended primary endpoint.
- **Cluster headache preventive:** Change from baseline in attack frequency (weekly for episodic CH, monthly for chronic CH) across the double-blind phase or pre-specified period. Rationale: IHS recommended primary endpoint for preventive treatment.
- **IHS adherence:** Assessment will determine whether primary/secondary endpoints recommended by the IHS were evaluated, and whether the prespecified primary and secondary outcomes recommended by the IHS were achieved.

Additional outcomes:

- **IHS recommended secondary outcome for each indication.**
- **Safety:** adverse events (AEs) and serious AEs.
- **Regulatory:** device authorisations (FDA clearance/CE marking).

Risk of bias in individual studies

The risk of bias will be assessed using the Cochrane RoB 2 tool. Data extraction and assessment will be performed independently by at least two reviewers. Any discrepancies will be resolved through discussion or consultation with a third reviewer.

Data synthesis

The synthesis will be structured as a summary of results, providing an overview of the characteristics of the included studies for each neuromodulation modality and treatment indication. The findings will be presented through a comprehensive narrative synthesis of the quantitative studies. If sufficient homogeneity is identified among the included studies, a meta-analysis will be performed.

Meta-bias(es)

Will not be performed

Confidence in cumulative evidence (GRADE)

The overall certainty of the evidence will be assessed using the GRADE (Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation) approach. This method evaluates the quality of evidence across studies for each outcome based on factors such as risk of bias, consistency, directness, precision, and publication bias.